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Co-creation and Indirect Approach as a Methodology to Improve Student Engagement in Initial and Continuing VET

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Abstract

This contribution intends to discuss the first results of the implementation of COSI.ed methodology in the improvement of students' motivation and aspirations, the relations of students and teachers, and student engagement in the context of VET centres managed by third-sector entities. For this purpose, 23 in-depth interviews were carried out to record the itineraries prior to entering VET, as well as their perceptions of the training received in VET. At the same time, the influence of VET centres' intervention on the perception of training and on youth aspirations and future expectations was analysed.

The results indicate that the training and attention received in VET have had an influence on greater confidence in educational institutions and in their possibilities and abilities, highlighting the positive influence of the relationship with teachers in this process. In addition, the results show a clarification of youth future expectations, both professional and personal.

Keywords

co-creation, indirect approach, youth at risk, VET

1 Introduction

The European strategic framework for education and training 2030 aims to reduce Early Leaving from Education and Training (ELET) to 9% (Council of the European Union, 2021). Spain is one of the countries in the European Union with one of the highest ELET standing at 13.3% in 2021, compared to the EU average of 9.7% (Eurostat, 2022)

In this context, many research studies highlight the strategic role of vocational education and training (VET) in reducing ELET (Cedefop, 2020; Marhuenda-Fluixá, 2019). This requires the development of innovative educational interventions and policies that allow for the development and transformation of the Spanish VET system, offering a more comprehensive range of training adapted both to the student's needs and to the demands of the labour market, and improving academic and vocational guidance.

In this paper, we present the first results of the project "CO-created Education through social inclusion (COSI.ed)"¹, an Erasmus+ project (KA3) funded by the European Commission and composed of a total of 11 partners and whose implementation period is 2021-2024. The main objective of the project is to reduce ELET by implementing an innovative socio-educational intervention methodology in different educational and geographical contexts through the application of Equal Literacy, Co-creation and Indirect Approach.

2 Theoretical framework and literature review

COSI.ed intervention model promotes a rethinking of the teaching and learning processes by situating students who have dropped out or are at risk of dropping out, at the centre, based on their own experiences and knowledge to promote the development of skills and competencies to contribute to the further development of their sense of self-efficacy. In turn, the project aims to improve the relations between teachers and students as an instrument to increase student's engagement with the educational centre.

To this end, three key theoretical pillars are taken into consideration in the intervention methodology: Equal Literacy, Indirect Approach, and Co-creation (Gravesen et al., 2021).

Equal Literacy refers to the theoretical construct that allows us to understand the pathways and processes followed by young people, taking into consideration the macro, meso and micro-structural elements that intervene in their configuration. This process allows us to understand the individuality of the pathways of young people at risk or in a situation of social exclusion, eliminating prejudices and stereotypes. In this way, we would take into account six interrelated factors of influence: the pre-existing context, the personal experiences lived, the positioning of others (how others perceive our trajectories), the technologies of oppression/liberation (mechanisms of reproduction of stereotypes and prejudices, the absence of these leads to liberation), the positioning of oneself (an attitude that the individual adopts towards the position in which society places him/her: victimhood, conformity, rebelliousness) and the impact of all the above elements on young people's pathways (Stuart et al., 2020).

A second pillar is *Indirect Approach*, a qualitative methodological approach that allows teachers to understand and capture students' processes, pathways and prior educational experiences through the use of unstructured interviews. Thus, a key element of the approach is the interviewer's indirect way of approaching the participant's life world, making sure not to introduce ideas, concepts or notions into the conversation that have not first been presented by the participant. In this way, the learner takes on the role of the narrator of his/her own story and guides the topics of the conversation at all times (Moshuus and Eide, 2016; Stuart et al., 2020).

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In this way, we achieve a global apprehension of the fact studied, adopting the point of view of the social actors, referring us to a concrete socio-structural reality, in which objective (caused by the environment) and subjective (caused by the actor subject) events occur that mark and modify the biographical itineraries, modifications produced not only by the event itself but also by the consciousness and the way in which the individual perceives and experiences them as well as his/her reaction to these events (Ryan and Lőrinc, 2018).

Finally, *Co-creation* is a methodological strategy consisting of the configuration of new knowledge, resulting from the interaction and integration of joint work between different actors. It is based on a process of analysis and open debate, transmultidisciplinary, based on the construction from the common factors that lie at the intersection of different approaches to an object, as opposed to interdisciplinary approaches that seek more the contribution to the whole, based on the inputs that each one brings from their own discipline; we do not speak therefore of "a puzzle" but of the integration of participation and mutual learning (Klein, 2013). The significance of one or other lines of intervention or key themes of the knowledge that is to be elaborated, integrated and shared must emerge from this work. The process implies a leading role of the participants, the intrinsic motivation to contribute imaginative and creative ideas directed at the core of the question, giving a role to the flexibility of the process itself, which can vary all the elements, until reaching the concretion of a participatory, shared and integrated knowledge. In the case of transdisciplinary research, three dimensions are considered: the consensus of shared interest, group cohesion to co-create knowledge and, finally, the result of a strengthened and socially integrated theoretical knowledge (Van Veen et al., 2013).

3 Methodology and framework of the research

This paper presents the first results obtained in Spain by the COSI.ed intervention model. Concretely, in the case of Mallorca (Balearic Islands, Spain), this initiative is applied in the field of VET centres managed by third-sector entities with extensive experience in offering Initial and Continuing VET aimed at young people over 16 years of age who have dropped out of the education system to offer training adapted to the needs of this profile of young people to improve both their professional qualification and their chances of finding employment. We consider testing this methodology in VET centres relevant as most of the students who arrive at these centres have experienced previous erratic educational itineraries, generally in compulsory secondary education. These seem to be the reasons which have led them to low confidence in the school institution, poor motivation towards training, and a loss of belief in their possibilities and potential.

We want to answer the following research questions: 1) What is the profile of the young people who attend these centres? 2) What are the characteristics of their previous educational pathways? 3) What are their motivations for attending these centres? 4) What aspects do they value of the training and attention received in these training centres? 5) What are their future expectations regarding training and labour market insertion?

Methodologically, in-depth interviews were conducted with 23 young people who started their training in the 2021-22 academic year in two VET centres: (1) Sociedad Cooperativa Jovent (or Jovent), and (2) Naüm Proyecto Socioeducativo (or Naüm). Both centres are located in the Balearic Islands, one of the Spanish regions with the highest early school leaving rates (Salvà-Mut *et al.*, 2014). Besides, we evaluated items related to student engagement, like academic performance and school assistance, at the beginning and the end of VET training.

The qualitative analysis of the participants' discourses was performed with the NVivo software by coding themes around: (1) students' profiles and life stories; (2) perception of their previous educational pathways; (3) academic and professional motivations and interests; (4) perception of their learning processes at VET centres; (5) and their perception and knowledge around their future professional and educational expectations.

The subsequent sections will feature pseudonyms in place of the participants' quotes to keep all the data anonymous and safeguard any personal information.

4 Results

Students' profiles and life stories

Notably, 23 students (14 from Jovent centre, in a Dual VET of Nautical Mechanics, and nine from Naüm centre in an Initial VET of Plumbing) have been interviewed, 22 men and one woman, aged between 16 and 28, and at-risk of social exclusion. It is particularly relevant to students' life stories and countries of origin to understand why they started at their VET centres.

In Jovent's case, six students (out of 14) emigrated from their home countries for socioeconomic reasons. They are from Argentina, Venezuela, Bolivia, Colombia, and Brazil. Both of them, Francisco and Cesar, have university degrees in their countries. However, their migration status forces them to start a new requalification process in Spain. Cesar's case is exceptional. He is 28 years old and finished a Business Administration Bachelor's Degree in Venezuela. However, even though Cesar emigrated to Spain to improve their professional and personal socioeconomic situation, he had tremendous difficulties finding a job in Mallorca, which led him to pursue Dual VET training in Jovent.

Carlos and Eduardo emigrate after obtaining their Secondary School certificate to improve their professional possibilities. However, both point out that they were subjected to racist discrimination by their peers when they tried to finish Secondary School in Mallorca.

Finally, Aitor and Alex interrupted their Secondary School in Venezuela and Colombia to emigrate with their families to Spain. In both cases, they end up at Jovent because of their economic needs and the facilities that Dual Training provides.

On the other hand, eight students (out of 14) of Jovent are from Mallorca. If we compare their life stories and educational pathways, we can deduce that their education (and personal) situation is significantly better: only two drop out of school during Secondary School. Four have a Secondary School certificate, and two have Upper Secondary School. The main reasons to drop out in their cases are focused on bad experiences with school teachers. All participants (except Pablo) considered these bad experiences with teachers as a source of a lack of motivation and bad academic results. Only Pablo highlights peer-to-peer issues as a cause of dropping out.

In Naüm's case, six students (out of 9) emigrated from their home countries for socioeconomic reasons, particularly Guinea Conakry, Morocco, and Algeria. However, unlike the Jovent students, they emigrated alone and as minors in situations of extreme vulnerability. For this reason, all of them live in juvenile centres, and they started in Naüm because of the referral and orientation they received from their respective juvenile centres. The remaining three students from Naüm are in similar situations to the young Mallorcans from Jovent. All three dropped out of secondary education because of poor relationships and experiences with teachers, linked to a significant lack of motivation and poor academic results.

Given the above, we can deduce that the life histories of these young people are determinant in their school experiences, that is, in their educational levels and future professional possibilities.

Educational pathways: perceptions and reflections on their passage through the educational system

Youth assessments of their school experiences before they arrived at VET centres were primarily negative. Exceptionally, two participants, Cesar and Amath, were satisfied and even nostalgic about their memories of their educational experiences. While Cesar was grateful for

the knowledge he gained from attending university in Venezuela, Amath was delighted and nostalgic, recalling his childhood in Guinea Conakry. The rest of the participants (21 out of 23 total) highlight negative aspects that mainly relate to teachers' excessive authority. Some of them link this authority to a lack of empathy and poor accompaniment by teachers.

The passage below shows Joel's dissatisfaction with his school experience. He mainly links his (general) demotivation to a bad relationship with the school, which is rigorous and supposedly biased towards individual student profiles like his.

Joel: The school was very rigid, I would ask to go to the bathroom, and they would expel me. One day I drank a bottle of water, I drank it, and they expelled me for a week, (...) that was in the first year of Secondary Education (...). They were very jealous of us, (...) although I didn't listen to them much either; if they didn't care about us, why should I listen to them?

In addition, five participants also criticise the excessive amount of theory and link it to extreme difficulty, translating into student demotivation. The passage below shows the demotivation and the bad memory that Asa has of his high school experience.

Asa: I remember the teachers and having a lot of homework always. I had no free time, and I said, "I don't want to be here; I want to leave". (...) They explained everything as very boring.

The results show that the youth educational pathways have been affected by certain shortcomings of the current educational system. Some of these shortcomings are the rigidity of the teaching staff and the universalisation of theoretical and traditional teaching as the only valid teaching option. This seems to generate low levels of motivation, which together with a significant lack of guidance from the educational centres, ends up causing early school dropouts.

Finally, it is worth noting the impact of COVID. Specifically, four students commented that the loss of "presence" at school meant a before and after in their academic concentration and motivation levels. In addition, during the interviews, two of them pointed out that they had problems with the Internet connection and even with the computer itself, making it difficult for them to interact and learn during the pandemic. This fact highlights that the digital divide has affected some students during the pandemic; for instance, certain structural inequalities have surfaced, such as the lack of digital devices and Internet connection. Those digital inequalities have made it difficult for them to adapt to the new virtual reality and have, therefore, negatively impacted their learning levels (Selwyn *et al.*, 2001).

Reasons to start at VET centres: how students arrived

As we have explained in the previous section, the socioeconomic and family context of the participants in this study has been a determining factor in their educational trajectories. Knowing this, it is also interesting to analyse how the young people have arrived at their respective VET centres. We distinguish five ways: (1) orientation by the youth centre, (2) recommendation by a close friend or relative, (3) by their interest and motivation, (4) orientation by the Balearic Islands Employment Service (SOIB), and (5) orientation by the educational centre.

The most repeated reason among the participants is the orientation through the centre for minors and the motivation and orientation by the circle of friends and family. Significantly, the last two positions are occupied by guidance from the school and the SOIB. This shows that the educational system needs to improve concerning early school leaving and the lack of advice

and support for students who drop out. These structural deficiencies reproduce class inequalities and significantly impact socially vulnerable groups, such as young people who do not receive or do not have close social and family support.

VET centres: opinions and students' perception

All participants were delighted with the VET training. They enjoy the theoretical and practical sessions and have good relationships with teachers and peers. These factors of improvement seem to have a positive impact on their motivation levels and self-esteem. All these positive perceptions are opposed to their past school experiences (except, in Cesar's case, the university graduate participant). There, “doing in school” changes in a significant positive way, becoming (even in Cesar’s case) an opportunity to learn and share a space with “good people”. Both passages below exemplify that participants, with any exceptions, have a reasonable opinion of what they do in VET centres and how they will take professional and personal advantage of their experiences and the relationships that they have created during the process:

Alex: Jovent is progress in my life; it is a big opportunity, at least for me

Cesar: for me, Jovent make a real difference in my life, with a before' and an after' (...), I'm taking emotions and learning. It's good to learn from my friends and teachers and study a field that was new for me, (...) so I have grown in terms of learning but also as a person

All the participants emphasise the motivation for the practical activities they carry out at the centre and the human touch they receive from all the centre staff. In addition, the guidance and student support processes applied with the Indirect Approach have resulted in trusting relationships between students and teachers:

Cristian: If you ask them [teachers] for help, they give it to you, you know? In high school, you asked for help, and no one came to help you...

As a result, the youth attendance levels at VET have improved significantly compared to school attendance levels. In addition, there is a noticeable improvement in the academic results of all participants and, consequently, in youth self-esteem:

Luis: Not only that you trust what you are doing, but also that you trust the people who are teaching you.

With these results, we can deduce that the intervention methodology of the COSI.ed, has had a positive impact on the students' level of motivation and performance, and also, as shown in the following section, on their imaginary future and professional expectations.

Imaginary future and professional expectations

All the participants had confused educational aspirations before starting in Jovent and Naüm centres. However, their motivation levels were high after VET, and their professional and academic expectations for their future considerably improved. Therefore, we can distinguish between three different profiles according to their imaginary futures and intentions: workers, trainees, and learners.

Firstly, the main profile (11 out of 23) is the student that prefers working after the VET course. This profile distinguishes those who prefer to work in a company and those with entrepreneurial aspirations. Practically all of them have the basic knowledge to achieve their goals and have discussed it with the professionals in their respective VET centres. Of the five

participants who intend to start their own business shortly, only one is aware of and claims to have the initial investment required for his business idea.

The second most common profile among students (7 out of 23) is those we have categorised as "trainees". They want to continue Training: working, and learning simultaneously to improve their qualifications and professional experiences. They intend to follow in the same sector, enhancing their educational merits and improving their future employment situation. In these cases, it seems that the Dual training structure has been a success for them, and they want to extend their experience with a view to the future.

The following passage is an example of the future aspirations of one of the students we have categorised as a trainee:

Amath: I want to work in a company and, at the same time, continue studying. When I finish in June, I will go for two weeks to do an internship in a company, and when I have my diploma, I would like to continue my Training.

The third profile is the minority; only five of the 23 students want to dedicate their next years exclusively to training. Therefore, we have categorised them as "learners". In this case, the students consider that the training provided by VET centres is insufficient to get what they consider a good job. Therefore, their commitment is to focus on improving their training and finding a qualified job in the future. It is encouraging that all profiles, without distinction, have significantly improved their self-esteem and motivation concerning their future. This improvement has been accompanied by a personalised orientation that has allowed them to share and discuss options about their expectations and career choices with teachers from VET. The results suggest that the VET experience has positively changed the students' self-image as learners and the educational alternatives that VET has provided them with.

5 Conclusions

The young people expressed in the interviews a strong disaffection with the school institution (especially throughout compulsory secondary education). They highly value the work carried out in the VET centres and especially emphasised the practicality of the training as well as the relationship established with their trainers, on many occasions stating that previously no one had been concerned about their state of mind, well-being or had received any kind of academic or professional guidance. Youth particularly value the role of teachers perceiving them as "colleagues" who support them in training and employment matters and on personal and family aspects.

Youth experience in VET seems to have marked a turning point in their perception of their training and professional possibilities. In this sense, the significant improvement in communication between the participants and teachers throughout the course is striking, thanks to the implementation of the Indirect Approach, which seems to have a direct impact on the students' motivation levels. Motivation also appears to be a decisive factor in the improvement of the participants' academic results and attendance levels. Therefore, we can conclude that the students' experience in VET has been a determining factor in their future professional expectations, as well as in their self-esteem.

Although this research shows certain limitations, as it is developed in a very specific context such as VETcentres in the Balearic Islands, the results obtained demonstrate the effectiveness of the methodology used in improving teacher-student relations, a fact that directly influences the students' increased confidence in their possibilities and abilities and in the definition of their future projects. This is why we believe that Co-creation and Indirect Approach could be included in VET policies and applied in similar geographical and educational contexts.

References

- Cedefop (2020). *Vocational Education and Training in Europe, 1995-2035: Scenarios for European Vocational Education and Training in the 21st Century. No 114*. Publications Office of the European Union. Cedefop reference series. <http://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2801/794471>
- EUROSTAT (2022). *Database. Early leavers from education and Training by sex and labour status*. https://appsso.eurostat.ec.europa.eu/nui/show.do?dataset=edat_lfse_14&lang=en
- Gravesen, D. T., Stuart, K., Bunting, M., Mikkelsen, S. H., & Frosthalm, P. H. (Eds.). (2021). *Combating marginalisation by co-creating education: methods, theories and practices from the perspectives of young people*. Emerald Group Publishing.
- Klein, J.T. (2013). The Transdisciplinary Moment(um). *Integral Review*, 9(2), 189-199.
- Marhuenda-Fluixá, F. (Ed.) (2019). *The School-Based Vocational Education and Training System in Spain: Achievements and Controversies. Vol. 32*. Springer. doi:10.1007/978-981-13-8475-2.
- Moshuus, G. H. & Eide, K. (2016). The indirect approach: How to discover context when studying marginal youth. *International journal of qualitative methods*, 15(1), 1-10.
- Ryan, L. & Lórin, M. (2018). Perceptions, prejudices and possibilities: young people narrating apprenticeship experiences. *British Journal of Sociology of Education*, 39(6), 762-777. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01425692.2017.1417821>.
- Salvà-Mut, F., Oliver-Trobat, M.F., & Comas-Forgas, R. (2014). Abandono escolar y desvinculación de la escuela: perspectiva del alumnado. *Magis, Revista Internacional de Investigación en Educación*, 6(13), 129-142.
- Selwyn, N., Gorard, S., & Williams, S. (2001). Digital Divide or Digital Opportunity? The Role of Technology in Overcoming Social Exclusion in U.S. Education. *Educational Policy*, 15(2), 258– 277. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0895904801015002002>
- Stuart, K., Bunting, M., Boyd, P., Cammack, P., Hornbæk Frosthalm, P., Thore Gravesen, D., Hølvig Mikkelsen, S., Moshuus, G., & Walker, S. (2020). Developing an equalities literacy for practitioners working with children, young people and families through action research. *Educational Action Research*, 28(3), 362-382.
- Van Veen, S.C., Bunders, J.F.G., & Regeer, B.J. (2013). Mutual learning for knowledge co-creation about disability inclusive development: experiences with a community of practice. *Knowledge Management for Development Journal*, 9(2) 105-124.

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